

What is the Association Between Social Isolation and Cardiovascular Disease Among Older Adults? A Systematic Review

by

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ABSTRACT

Introduction:

This dissertation investigates the impact of social isolation and loneliness on cardiovascular disease (CVD) incidence among older adults aged 65 years and above. It highlights the public health significance of social isolation as a psychosocial determinant influencing heart failure, stroke, and related cardiovascular outcomes.

Methods:

A systematic review was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines. Peer-reviewed primary studies published between 2017 and 2024 were identified through Medline, PubMed, CINAHL Ultimate, the British Heart Foundation (BHF), and WHO databases. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were based on the PICO framework, and study quality was assessed using the JBI and CASP tools. Data were synthesised narratively to evaluate methodological quality and summarise the findings.

Results and Discussion:

Thirteen studies were included, comprising prospective cohort, cross-sectional, and randomized field trial designs. Findings consistently demonstrated that loneliness and reduced social connections were associated with increased risks of heart failure, CVD incidence, and mortality. Social isolation also correlated with depressive symptoms and poor quality of life among the elderly. Studies suggested that enhancing social support, promoting digital inclusion, and encouraging community engagement could mitigate these risks.

Conclusion:

The review concludes that social isolation and loneliness are significant modifiable risk factors for cardiovascular diseases among the elderly. Interventions fostering social connectedness, volunteering, and digital engagement can improve both cardiovascular and mental health outcomes. Integrating social well-being metrics into public health and clinical cardiovascular care frameworks is essential for effective prevention strategies.

Keywords:

Social Isolation; Loneliness; Cardiovascular Disease; Elderly; Public Health; Systematic Review; Quality of Life

1. Introduction:

The general term "cardiovascular disease" refers to conditions that affect the heart and circulatory system, as well as significant incidents such as blood clots or low oxygen levels caused by peripheral vessels, and vascular illnesses such as atherosclerosis or heart vessel blockages. These disorders can lead to several heart disorders, including myocardial infarction, cardiac failure, atrial fibrillation, and pulmonary embolism and in extreme cases, they can even be disastrous (NICE, 2023). Between 1990 to 2019, the overall number of people worldwide who suffered from cardiovascular illnesses increased from 271 million in 1990 to 523 million in 2019. Ischemic heart disease and stroke raised the number of people with disability-adjusted life years to 142 million and 183 million, respectively (Roth *et al.*, 2020). In the UK, about 7.6 million people have cardiovascular disease (British Heart Foundation, 2023). High blood pressure can lead to serious heart and blood vessel issues, which can include heart failure, angina, atrial fibrillation, and heart attacks. As there are approximately 1.28 billion people with high blood pressure globally, ranging in age from 30 to 79, and two-thirds of these people belong to middle-class or lower-income nations (WHO, 2021).

One of the prominent factors that can have detrimental impacts on the health conditions, especially cardiac health, of older adults, is living alone, as the level of engagement and regularity of one's interpersonal relationships describes social isolation, whereas the word loneliness relates to subjective solidarity sensations (Hwang *et al.*, 2020). Also, social isolation refers to the objective state of people's social contexts and reduced social interaction, whereas loneliness is a subjective perception of feeling isolated (Hwang *et al.*, 2020). While temporary loneliness is frequent, prolonged or severe loneliness can be harmful to one's mental and physical well-being (Surkalim *et al.*, 2022). Even more detrimental are the ongoing (longer than four years) effects of being alone and socially detached, which include reduced activity levels, mental activity declination, impaired cardiovascular fitness, trouble sleeping, cerebrovascular accident, and cardiovascular disease, coupled with higher blood pressure, depressive symptoms, increased body weight, increased use of cigarettes, alcohol and drug, and alone time (Berg-Weger and Morely, 2020). Elderly loneliness has also been linked to less

multigenerational living, less territorial accessibility, and fewer connected communities (Fakoya, McCorry and Donnelly, 2020). Older people who do not have many social relationships, or are considered socially disconnected, or who feel dissatisfied with their social lives, or who are isolated, are more likely to die at younger-old age, and these findings are linked to shortcomings in connections with others and a greater likelihood of coronary artery disease and stroke among them (Valtorta *et al.*, 2016). The likelihood of social isolation rises with ageing because of retirement status and being widowed, among other life variables, as a staggering 25% of American seniors 65 years of age and over reported being isolated from society, while the probability of loneliness ranged from 22% to 47% (American Heart Association, 2022). Social isolation directly affects the health of individuals by increasing the chance of mortality at a young age, 50% greater likelihood of dementia, 29% higher chance of cardiovascular disease, and 32% higher incidence of having a stroke (Manjunath, Manoj and Alchalabi, 2021). As cardiovascular diseases, social isolation, and loneliness are major public health concerns, in addition to their positive correlation among older adults, especially from the Covid pandemic period, they also represent a larger expense to healthcare for treatments and doctor visits for the elderly. Hence, this systematic review explores public health issues and their associated impacts among the elderly.

The goal of this systematic review is to examine the most current findings on how loneliness and social isolation affect older people's risk of cardiovascular disease. Additionally, the objective is to shed light on the detrimental impacts of loneliness and social isolation on the quality of life among the elderly, as well as highlight the necessity for medical professionals to ensure early interventions, such as social support, to avoid cardiovascular disease and its repercussions.

2. Methods:

2.1 Research design:

Systematic review design has been used because it assembles primary data and compiles all pertinent findings currently available. (Siddaway, Wood and Hedges, 2019). Also, it is an organised compilation of findings from searches, along with an assessment of the quantity, type, and quality of the evidence available in relation to a specific research question. Systematic reviews are distinguished by an orderly, comparable approach and by the manner of presentation. (Siddaway, Wood and Hedges, 2019) It compiles all primary research findings released for review and follows a predictable approach that outlines the criteria used to identify studies and determine whether to include or exclude them (Phillips and Barker, 2021). The realisation that systematic reviews offer the greatest degree of precision, transparency, and comprehensiveness in the literature helps gauge their value (Li, Saldanha and Robinson, 2022). Clarifying objectives and techniques in a research procedure, locating appropriate studies, compiling acquired information, evaluating the quality of the research, integrating evidence-based data, and comprehending results are important steps in developing successful systematic reviews. (Pollock and Berge, 2018). PRISMA's 2020 guidelines and flowchart outline enhanced standards of reporting for systematic reviews that consider improvements in identifying, assessing, assembling, and prioritising publications (Page *et al*, 2021).

2.2 Search strategy:

2.2.1. Databases and other literature resources:

To find the latest studies on social isolation as a risk factor for incidence of CVD among the elderly above 65 years of age from a global perspective, a literature search was done in the electronic databases Medline, PubMed, CINAHL ultimate, British Heart Foundation (BHF) and the World Health Organisation (WHO) website.

2.2.2. Publication years:

Research of the literature covering the last seven years (2017–2024) has been conducted since these publications provide the most recent data about the trends in social isolation among older individuals and the development patterns and statistics of heart disease as covid pandemic was during these seven years and it added highest worsening impacts and long tail after-effects relating to social isolation and loneliness particularly among older adults.

2.2.3. Countries included:

As these developed nations are the UK, China, Belgium, and America, a selection of geographical regions was made primarily to examine global perspectives on social isolation as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Specifically, the goal was to compare the incidence of heart disease among socially isolated elderly populations across various regions.

2.2.4. Boolean operators and keywords:

The three Boolean operators AND, OR, and NOT are named after the mathematician George Boole, who used them for relevant literature searches with specific search terms. (Grewal, Kataria and Dhawan, 2016). Using keywords, Boolean operators "AND" and "OR", quotation marks and asterisks have been used in database literature searches. The structure, terminology, and implementation of Boolean operators are as follows:

"Cardiovascular diseases" OR "heart diseases" OR "heart failure" AND "social isolation" OR "lack of social support" OR "loneliness" OR "social exhaustion" AND "elder*" OR "older adults" OR "above 65 years old"

"Cardiovascular diseases" OR "cardiac issues" OR "heart attack" AND "old people" OR "older adults" AND "social detachment" OR "social exclusion"

2.3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

This systematic review includes and excludes studies based on the PICO framework.

2.3.1. Inclusion criteria:

- Individuals recognised as having a higher chance of developing cardiovascular disorders and dying because of heart diseases Cené *et al.* (2012); Coyte *et al.*, (2022); Chen *et al.*, (2024).
- Extensive research available about the frequency of social isolation in the elderly population, (Coyte *et al.*, 2022).
- Studies that have been published in journals with peer review.
- Research evaluating social support after social isolation intervention as a means of lowering heart disease rates in the senior population

2.3.2. Exclusion criteria:

- Research results that are not readily available in English to preserve coherence and promote understanding while extracting and analysing data.
- Studies with insufficient numbers of participants or inadequate information might jeopardise the validity and consistency of the conclusions.

2.3.3. PICO framework:

PICO	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	older adults aged 65 years and above	Children, Younger adults, middle-aged people
Intervention	Research shows a correlation between the emergence of cardiovascular disorders and a lack of social support, or social isolation.	Research that dismisses addressing the relationship between social isolation and cardiovascular problems in older individuals
Comparison	senior citizens who are socially isolated (lonely)	senior citizens without social isolation
Outcome	Cardiovascular disease development and poor quality of life	Studies that focus on other medical conditions

Table 1

Significance of the PICO tool:

According to Abdulazeez Eldawlatly *et al.* (2018), PICO (Patient/Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome) is an organised framework frequently used in evidence-based clinical studies to design investigations and guide systematic searches for relevant literature. Researchers can identify evidence-based solutions for specific health and wellness issues using the PubMed PICO tool, which supports the literature review and evidence-gathering process. (Brown, 2019). This helps to minimise bias and guarantee the validity of the results, as indicated in Table 1.

2.3.4. Justification of inclusion criteria:

Age group: Older adults over 65 years of age have been chosen because they experience social isolation more frequently than those in younger age groups, and loneliness increases the risk of cardiovascular disease in them more often than young people (Coyte *et al.*, 2022; Czaja, Moxley and Rogers, 2021; Guo *et al.*, 2023)

Social isolation has been considered with the aim of examining its catastrophic consequences, including cardiovascular diseases among older adults. The reason is that social isolation is a major public health concern among the elderly population, leading to the development of various life-threatening conditions, including heart disease and mental disorders.

2.4. Study screening:

The first stage of the screening process involved evaluating the titles and abstracts of 350 articles to determine their relevance to the study subject. Articles that had few duplicates were eliminated. A thorough review of the literature was conducted at this stage, also known as Phase 1 and Phase 2 screening.

2.4.1. Phase 1 screening:

180 articles were screened.

- Evaluated the article titles and abstracts
- Collected publications that seemed to be relevant to the search question.

- Articles that satisfied the first screening requirement were added to the Phase 2 screening (67 articles).

2.4.2. Phase 2 screening:

67 articles were screened.

- Determined final eligibility by using the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Any disagreements or ambiguities about the inclusion of an item were settled by discussion and conclusion.
- Articles were eliminated on the grounds of secondary research and ineffective information (34 articles).
- Additional research findings were disregarded as the complete text was unavailable, and the study was not question-focused (20 articles).

2.4.3. Final studies included:

Thirteen publications were incorporated in this systematic review after they satisfied the inclusion criteria.

2.5. Data extraction:

PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) flow chart, sometimes called a PRISMA flow diagram, is an organisational tool which illustrates the procedures needed to conduct a systematic review and analysis (Page *et al.*, 2021). Recognition, evaluation, eligibility assessment, and inclusion of studies are all parts of these processes. The PRISMA diagram provides a thorough summary of how the data flows across the many phases of a systematic review. It shows the number of records found, added, and removed, along with the justifications for any removals. (Calderon Martinez *et al.*, 2023).

The subsequent data items were extracted systematically:

- The publishing year
- Name of the author
- Study design
- Aim of the research

- participants' particulars
- Outcome metrics (mortality linked to CVD, incidence)
- Study findings.
- Suggestions on clinical implementation.
- Proposals for further investigation.

2.6. Quality appraisal:

Both the JBI (Joanna Briggs Institute) and CASP (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme) frameworks have been employed for the quality appraisal. For researchers looking to conduct systematic reviews or critically examine scientific literature, JBI provides a range of openly accessible tools for critical analysis. (Barker *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, the instruments employed are arranged as a checklist, assessing whether a study meets a predetermined set of requirements, and the answers to these questions may be yes, no, unclear, or not relevant.

(Barker *et al.*, 2023). The CASP checklist is another critical evaluation tool for literature searches, consisting of 12 assessment questions to determine the study's reliability and inform the ultimate decision about whether to include it in the research. It is used for non-randomised controlled trials, cohort studies, and case-control studies. (Ma *et al.*, 2020). According to Tadesse Gebrye *et al.* (2023), quality evaluation plays a critical role in ensuring the accuracy of research findings, identifying potential biases, and enhancing the overall reliability and validity of the systematic review.

The quality of prospective cohort studies using CASP checklists was examined, and the studies involved were (Golaszewski *et al.*, 2022; Cené *et al.*, 2012; Coyte *et al.*, 2022; Yarish *et al.*, 2024; Christiansen *et al.*, 2021; Guo *et al.*, 2023; Chen *et al.*, 2024).

Maximum of the include studies were of high quality because they answered most the questions of the checklist effectively, addressed the public health issue, exposure and outcome were measured to minimize bias, results of the studies were reliable and measured with the effective measuring scales, fitting with other available literature except for one study (Guo *et al.*, 2023) which had not taken into consideration the confounding factors in analysis section and just analysed straightforward factors.

The quality appraisal using the JBI checklist was done for the studies (Figueiredo *et al.*, 2020; Hu *et al.*, 2021; Uchmanowicz *et al.*, 2020; Zhu *et al.*, 2023; Jo, Ji Seo and Son, 2020). Two of the included studies (Jo, Ji Seo and Son, 2020; Figueiredo *et al.*, 2020) addressed most of the research questions effectively and were of high quality, whereas three did not meet the criteria for high quality. The study by Uchmanowicz *et al.* (2020; Zhu *et al.*, 2023) did not identify confounding factors, and Uchmanowicz *et al.* (2020) did not address strategies to properly measure them, while another study by Hu *et al.* (2021) did not authentically measure exposure and outcomes. Another study by Czaja, Moxley and Rogers (2021), a randomised field trial, was also appraised as high quality by the JBI checklists. Appendices 1 and 2 contain CASP and JBI checklists.

2.7. Data analysis:

Integrating narratively, the findings of the research involve more than just listing or describing each study's key findings; they also involve summarising, discussing, and evaluating each study's methodological quality to minimise potential discrimination (Ryan, 2013). Being proficient with the findings of the included studies is a necessary first step in narrative synthesis, and this entails systematically and thoroughly evaluating each study's findings, emphasising key findings where appropriate, such as significant parallels or discrepancies (Ryan, 2013). Narrative synthesis of empirical data is frequently the preferred approach when statistical synthesis is not feasible (Campbell *et al.*, 2018). A narrative synthesis strategy was used for data analysis in this systematic review of cardiovascular illnesses among older people caused by social isolation. This approach is regularly employed in systematic reviews to bring together outcomes from various research (Lisy and Porritt, 2016). To address the review's research questions and objectives, the extracted data, including study characteristics, participant statistics, intervention particulars, outcome metrics, research findings, and recommendations, were systematically integrated. The combination of both qualitative and quantitative information from different research designs was made possible using narrative synthesis, which is renowned for its adaptability and universality (Lisy and Porritt, 2016).

3. Results:

The principal findings of the study on the prevalence of cardiovascular illnesses caused by social isolation and loneliness, as well as the CVDs that cause mortality among older individuals, are discussed here. The influence of several causes of social isolation and the lack of social support, as well as interventions to provide social assistance to individuals, was studied through a thorough review and synthesis of the current research. The goal is to broaden understanding regarding the role social support plays in reducing CVD in older individuals throughout the world.

3.1. Search results:

Two stages of screening were conducted on the search results. First, databases were used to identify 350 search results: 341 from electronic databases and 9 from other search resources. Automation techniques identified 90 search results as ineligible and eliminated 80 duplicate searches. Of the 180 items remaining for phase 1 screening, 113 were disqualified because they didn't meet the inclusion criteria. Phase 2 screenings included evaluating 67 search results for titles and abstracts, eliminating 12 papers for irrelevant data, and excluding 22 publications as systematic reviews, meta-analyses, review articles, and secondary studies. 33 publications remained at this point, of which 12 were eliminated because they did not address the research question and 8 because full text could not be retrieved. Finally, 13 population-based primary studies are included in this systematic review, which presents a wide variety of research examining the connection between social exclusion and the risk of cardiovascular disease in older people. This is shown in the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1), which monitors the management of research data throughout the systematic evaluation approach.

(Rethlefsen and Page, 2022) As follows:

3.1.1. PRISMA flow diagram:

Figure 1. Prisma flow diagram

3.2. Summary of studies:

The research encompassed many studies with varying methods, sample sizes, geographic locations, and participant demographics. The systematic review used a range of research designs, such as cross-sectional studies, randomised controlled trials (RCTs), prospective cohort studies, and longitudinal analyses.

The included research on geographical dispersion, spanning a range of locations, added to the topic's global perspective. By considering significant cultural and geographic disparities in the efficiency of providing social support to older adults to

lower their risk of heart disease and improve their health outcomes, this worldwide representation significantly strengthened the systematic review.

3.2.1. Table of characteristics:

Number	First author, year	Aim of the study	Participants and their location	Design and methods	Measures	Key results	Study quality
Theme 1	The relationship between social isolation and the prevalence of cardiovascular disorders						
1	Cené, 2012	Incident of heart failure (HF) and social isolation with consideration of exhaustion among the elderly	12,995 participants from the four US communities	The Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities (ARIC) study is a prospective cohort study that uses Cox proportional-hazards models and data collected during hospital visits.	The Lubben Social Network Scale is used to quantify social isolation and vital exhaustion, and to measure them using mediation analysis.	Higher social isolation and incident HF are highly mediated by vital weariness.	High
2	Coyte, 2022	Determining the correlation between low social ties and the frequency of HF	3698 males from GPs in 24 British locations, aged 60-79,	Prospective study design. Data collection using a questionnaire: A lifestyle and medical questionnaire,	Evaluation of data based on social relationship, satisfaction with contact, and frequency of contact scores. Cox proportional hazard models were used to analyse the risk of incident HF.	Out of the 3698 people, 330 had heart failure. Men were more likely to encounter HF incidence when they had fewer family connections.	High
3	Yarish, 2024	Exploring incidents of cardiovascular disease (CVD) and social isolation and loneliness in ageing non-veteran and veteran women	52,442 female veterans and non-veterans from the US	Prospective cohort study	Cox proportional-hazards models were used to estimate HR and 95% CI for the Interquartile Range (IQR) in social isolation.	The findings showed that among women, social isolation and loneliness and CVD were negatively connected in a similar way for both veterans and non-veterans, but the association was stronger for veterans.	High

4	Golaszewski, 2022	investigating the relationship between postmenopausal women's experiences of CVD and their social isolation and loneliness.	57,825 US healthy women aged 65 to 99	prospective cohort study from the Women's Health Initiative Extension Study II	To determine hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals for CVD among women with high vs low social isolation and loneliness ratings, multivariable Cox proportional hazards regression models were employed.	Women with high ratings for loneliness and social isolation had incident CVD risks ranging from 13.0% to 27.	High
5	Guo, 2023	correlation between middle-aged and older people's social isolation behaviours and incident CVD	8422 participants mean age of 59 years, from China	Cohort Study Design	Cox proportional-hazards models were used to evaluate the association between social isolation patterns and the risk of incident CVD.	Over the 4-year follow-up, 746 incident CVDs were reported. Following demographic adjustments, individuals with variable and consistently high social isolation had higher incident CVD risks than those with consistently low social isolation.	High
6	Christiansen, 2021	Identifying associations between social isolation (SI) and psychological and cardiovascular disease (CVD) incidences	24,687 participants from Denmark	Prospective cohort study of self-reported data and individual-level data with a follow-up period of 2013-2018	Cox proportional hazard regression analysis and Multiple mediation analyses	A multiple mediation investigation demonstrated an indirect relationship between loneliness and SI and CVD. SI and loneliness have been separately associated with CVD.	High
7	Hu, 2021	relationship between isolation and loneliness and	11,498 healthy Australians over the age of 70	ASpirin in Reducing Events in the Elderly (ASPREE) trial and the	Framingham Risk Score (FRS) and	Larger ASCVD risk scores were linked to loneliness (women: $p < 0.05$; men:	medium

		social support as CVD risk factors in healthy older persons		ASPREE Longitudinal Study of Older Persons	Atherosclerotic CVD Risk Scale (ASCVDRS).	p < 0.001), and larger FRS was linked to social isolation (women: p < 0.01; men: p < 0.01).	
Theme 2	severity of heart failure and social isolation among the elderly, reducing their quality of life and causing mortality						
8	Figueiredo, 2020	investigating the contributing elements that make patients with HF have a lower quality of life (QoL)	99 patients from the Cardiology Department of the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Belgium.	Cross-sectional study, The Minnesota Living with Heart Failure Questionnaire (MLwHF) and sociodemographic and clinical questionnaires for evaluation of QoL	to determine statistical and clinical significance, two multivariate models, the parametric beta regression analysis and the non-parametric regression tree, the hospital anxiety and depression scale (HADS)	QoL of patients with HF was found to be negatively impacted by anxiety and sadness, as per beta regression. MLwHF was negatively impacted by the New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional classes III and IV as per the regression tree	High
9	Czaja, 2021	essential components predicting social isolation and loneliness, as well as health and wellness markers relevant to interpersonal support, societal exclusion, and loneliness.	300 individuals from the United States, aged 65 to 98	PRISM (Personal Reminder, Information, and Social Management) randomised field trials	Using demographic information and self-reported data, the following indices were calculated: The UCLA Loneliness Scale, the Centre for Epidemiological Depression Scale (CESD), the Friendship Scale for Social Isolation, the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL) for Social Support, the	The sole component that could predict health, according to the Structural Equation Model for Health, was loneliness; a large social network was associated with lower levels of loneliness, whereas higher levels of loneliness were associated with worse self-ratings of health.	High

					Luben Social Network Index for Social Network Size, and the Centre for Epidemiological Depression Scale for Depressive Symptoms.		
10	Uchmanowicz, 2020	association between Frailty syndrome (FS) and the incidence of anxiety and depression among the elderly with Atrial Fibrillation (AF).	100 elderly patients (69 females, 31 males, mean age 70 years from Poland	Cross-sectional study	The Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) is used to measure depression, and the Tilburg Frailty Indicator (TFI) is used to measure FS.	Based on GDS scores, 51% of patients reported having signs of depression. Based on HADS scores, 20% of patients reported having anxiety symptoms and 28% reported having depressive symptoms.	Medium
11	Chen, 2024	Examining social isolation, loneliness, incident cardiovascular disease, all-cause mortality, CVD mortality, and cardiac function.	18,258 participants aged 38–73 years from the UK	Prospective, population-based cohort research, UK Biobank	Experience evaluation longitudinally using a questionnaire from the Centre for Epidemiologic Studies, the Depression scale, and a social isolation index score ranging from 0 to 3.	After an average follow-up period of 8.3 years, consistent social isolation was associated with a higher risk of incident CVD, all-cause, and CVD mortality when compared to never social isolation, with 3707 incident CVD cases and 856 deaths. An increased risk of severe cardiovascular illness, all-cause death, and death from heart disease has been associated with persistent loneliness.	High

Theme 3	Older cardiac patients' inclination to search for health-related information online and the impact of self-care and social support on improving health outcomes						
12	Jo, 2020	to clarify the relationship between health education, social support, and self-care in older adults with heart failure.	252 older adults from a tertiary care facility in South Korea	A cross-sectional descriptive study.	data collected through medical record reviews and structured questionnaires; data analysed using the hierarchical regression analysis technique	Health education and social assistance were shown to be significant determinants of self-care behaviours in older adults with heart failure, accounting for 22% of the variance.	High
13	Zhu, 2023	The degrees of self-efficacy, social support, and online health-related information searching among elderly patients with coronary heart disease	451 elderly cardiac patients in China	Cross-sectional and survey-based design. Data collection through a self-reporting sociodemographic questionnaire	Data analysis using structural equation modeling and the Patients Engagement Evaluation, Self-Efficacy Scale, Social Support Rating Scale, and Online Medical Information Acquisition Scale	Online health information seeking was directly impacted by patient activation ($p < .05$), social support ($p < .05$), and self-efficacy ($p < .05$).	Medium

3.3. Characteristics of the included studies:

Out of the 13 searches included in this systematic review, five are cross-sectional, one is a randomised controlled/field trial, and seven are population-based prospective cohort studies. Regardless of gender, participant samples ranged from 99 to 57,825 individuals, all of whom were older adults aged 60 and older. The Framingham Risk Score (FRS) and the Atherosclerotic CVD Risk were among the methods used for the evaluation and assessment of the data for the systematic review by (Hu *et al.*, 2021). Other methods of evaluation included the multivariable Cox proportional hazards regression models used in five studies by Yarish *et al.* (2024); Guo *et al.* (2023); Christiansen *et al.* (2021); Golaszewski *et al.* (2022); Coyte *et al.* (2022), the GDS and the HADS used by Uchmanowicz *et al.*, (2020) Hierarchical regression analysis is used by Jo, Ji Seo and Son (2020) , the Frequency of Contact's score, the Satisfaction with Contact's score, and the Social Relationship score used by Coyte *et al.* (2022), the CESD, social isolation (the Friendship Scale), loneliness (the UCLA Loneliness Scale), social support by ISEL and for the size of the social network (Lubben Social Network Index) used by Czaja, Moxley and Rogers (2021), the structural equations modelling for data analysis used by Zhu *et al.* (2023), the Epidemiologic Studies Depression scale, and a social isolation index score used by Chen *et al.* (2024).

Participants in the study originated from a variety of countries, including the US, China, the UK (England, Scotland, and Wales), Australia, Denmark, and the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, as well as veteran and non-veteran groups from the US and other countries. Apart from one study by Cené *et al.* (2012), selected for its noteworthy and significant results, the publication dates of the other studies ranged from 2020 to 2024. There was no gender-based prejudice because some included participants of both genders, others focused only on males, and others focused only on women.

Overall, the research encompassed a wide range of methodological approaches and participant demographics, offering insights into the relationship between social isolation and the prevalence of cardiovascular disorders among the elderly. However, when interpreting results and extrapolating to larger populations, it is crucial to consider changes in research design, sample size, and participant demographics.

3.4. Summary of findings:

Theme 1: The correlation between the incidence of cardiovascular illnesses and social isolation:

Seven of the included studies have discussed the effect of social isolation leading to the incidence of cardiovascular diseases and heart failure among the elderly, though some of these studies are different from each other in certain aspects, and the comparison is given as follows:

Almost all seven studies in this theme used a prospective cohort study design (Yarish *et al.*, 2024; Golaszewski *et al.*, 2022; Christiansen *et al.*, 2021; Cené *et al.*, 2012; Coyte *et al.*, 2022; Guo *et al.*, 2023) except for (Hu *et al.*, 2021) which used the ASPREE trials and longitudinal design. While determining an association between CVD, social isolation, and loneliness was the common goal of all the research, there were also a few other objectives, as Golaszewski *et al.*, (2022) Considering modifications in health-related habits and their consequences, Christiansen *et al.* (2021) examined psychological variables that impact social isolation and CVD incidence, and Yarish *et al.* (2024) focused more on veteran status. There were variations between the geographical research areas, as three studies, Cené *et al.*, (2012); Golaszewski *et al.*, (2022); Yarish *et al.*, (2024) were conducted in the U.S.; Coyte *et al.*, (2022) carried out investigations in the U.K.; Hu *et al.*, (2021) carried out research in Australia; Christiansen *et al.*, (2021) targeted population from Denmark and Guo *et al.*, (2023) selected China for research.

The population size also varied: Golaszewski *et al.* (2022) evaluated 57,825 older US women with a mean age of 79 years, the largest sample; Coyte *et al.* (2022) tested 3698 males aged 60 to 79, with an average age of 15.9 years, the smallest sample. While Cené *et al.* (2012) examined 12,995 participants irrespective of the gender for a roughly 18-year follow-up period, Christiansen *et al.*, (2021) investigated 24,687 participants, age 35 to 79, Hu *et al.*, (2021) had 11,498 healthy Australians aged 70 years or older in the research, study of Yarish *et al.*, (2024) comprised 52,442 females

(mean age, 79 years) and 89% veterans, throughout a 5.8-year period of follow up and Guo *et al.*, (2023) included 8422 participant with mean age 60 years.

Regarding data collection, validated questionnaires were used by Golaszewski *et al.* (2022) and lifestyle and medical questionnaire by Coyte *et al.* (2022) Hospitalisation data from hospital visits were used by Cené *et al.* (2012), questionnaires were sent to participants at the beginning of 2013 (either online or on hardcopy) by Christiansen *et al.*, (2021), Hu *et al.*, (2021) utilised data from the ASPREE Longitudinal Study of Older Persons sub-study, Guo *et al.*, (2023) utilised data fourth wave of the China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study.

There were different methods of data evaluation among the researchers, for example, (Cené *et al.*, 2012; and Christiansen *et al.*, 2021) used the mediation analysis method, Cox proportional hazard models were utilized by Coyte *et al.*, 2022; Christiansen *et al.*, (2021); Yarish *et al.*, (2024); Guo *et al.*, (2023); Golaszewski *et al.*, (2022) to measure the risk of incident heart failure and the variables of frequency of contact, satisfaction with contact, and social relationship. The 21-item Maastricht Questionnaire was used to assess physiological exhaustion (Cené *et al.* (2012) and the 10-item Lubben Social Network Scale, a well-justified tool that gauges the extent of an individual's active social network and their perception of solidarity from relatives, close friends, and neighbors, was used to quantify social isolation by (Cené *et al.*, 2012; Czaja, Moxley and Rogers, 2021). Moreover, Hu *et al.*, (2021) employed the Framingham Risk Score (FRS) and the Atherosclerotic CVD Risk Scale (ASCVDRS) for data measurements. However, Coyte *et al.*, (2022) used additional measures, including frequency of Contact score, Satisfaction with Contact score, and Social Relationship score.

The study results depicted were generally common, as 330 men (8.9%) of the total sample experienced incidental heart failure episodes, and those who had heart failure reported a higher incidence of low-frequency contact scores (13.5%) than those who did not experience cardiac failure (9.3%) (Coyte *et al.*, 2022). Meanwhile, in the study by Cené *et al.* (2012), 1727 incident heart attacks occurred, and the participants were categorised as follows: 362 individuals were classified as socially isolated, 733 as high risk, 1803 as moderate risk, and 10,097 as low risk. Similarly, in the study population of

Golaszewski et al. (2022), social isolation and loneliness were associated with 8.0% and 5.0% greater risks of incident CVD, respectively. In addition to it, Compared to women who experienced less social isolation and loneliness, those who had greater levels of social isolation and loneliness had an incident CVD risk that ranged from 13.0% to 27.0% higher. A comparable trend of reduced satisfaction of the interpersonal contacts was observed in individuals who experienced heart failure compared to those who did not (Heart failure in 17.6% versus No heart failure among 11.9%) and heart failure patients reported greater percentages of poor overall Social Interaction outcomes (Coyte *et al.*, 2022).

The following characteristics were identified as possible contributing variables: relatively older, mostly male, more likely Black, more likely to possess fewer qualifications beyond a high school certificate, and a higher probability of being current smokers, were the characteristics of the moderate or high or isolated group (Cené *et al.*, 2012). During the data evaluation, multiple medical conditions, taking medications, and socioeconomic and psychological characteristics were identified as possible contributing variables in the models in addition to self-reported characteristics, including ethnicity/study society, sexual orientation, academic achievement, alcohol usage at that time, and smoking habits (Cené *et al.*, 2012). The social support measured by a questionnaire was examined as a possible impact modifier. However, it was discovered that social support did not significantly alter relationships. (Golaszewski *et al.*, 2022) Moreover, it was the unique feature of this study. According to the theoretical terms by Cené *et al.* (2012), social separation functions as a source of stress that creates vital exhaustion, a condition of continuous psychological discomfort that has detrimental effects on behaviours that promote health and can result in heart attacks.

The study by Christiansen et al. (2021) found that loneliness and social isolation increased the likelihood of a CVD diagnosis by 30% and 24%, respectively, among participants. The fully optimised Cox proportional hazards regression analysis showed that, once all sociodemographic and causal factors were included in the model, neither social isolation nor loneliness was associated with receiving a CVD diagnosis; however, individuals with both social isolation and loneliness had significantly higher CVD risk

(Christiansen *et al.*, 2021). Consistent with the theme, Hu *et al.* (2021) found that men were less likely than women to feel lonely, but more likely than women to be socially isolated and to lack social support. Being lonely was linked to higher ASCVDRS in both men and women, regardless of the degree of social isolation and or social support (Hu *et al.*, 2021).

(Yarish *et al.*, 2024; Guo *et al.*, 2023) concluded the comparable results of the correlation between CVD events, social isolation, and loneliness; however, Yarish *et al.*, (2024) concluded that Veteran women claimed to be more socially isolated than non-veterans and Veteran status as an impact adjuster was examined, which was linked to more prevalent cases of CVD. Moreover, Guo *et al.*, (2023) concluded that out of the 8422 people (mean age 60 years), 4219 (50.09%) were men. While many participants (5267 out of 8422, 62.54%) consistently reported low social isolation, 16.62% (1400 out of 8422) had consistently high social isolation throughout the exposure. Over the course of the 4-year follow-up, there were 746 incident CVDs (450 heart disease events and 336 stroke cases) (Guo *et al.*, 2023).

Theme 2: The Severity of heart failure and social isolation among the elderly reduces their quality of life and causes mortality:

This theme included four research studies (Figueiredo *et al.*, 2020; Uchmanowicz *et al.*, 2020; Chen *et al.*, 2024; Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers, 2021), which yielded somewhat varied results with commonalities, using various analytic methodologies and population sizes. Researchers Figueiredo *et al.*, (2020) and Uchmanowicz *et al.*, (2020) had determined the main correlated factors that led to a decline in patients' quality of life and the development of depression symptoms in those with HF and AF. Furthermore, Chen *et al.* (2024) assessed CVD and associated factors, including CVD mortality. However, Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers (2021) looked at the relationship between low health scores, the incidence of mental diseases, including depression, and cardiac patients' lower QoL (quality of life). Both Figueiredo *et al.*, (2020) and Uchmanowicz *et al.*, (2020) employed comparable cross-sectional research designs. Nevertheless, Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers (2021) used a completely different methodology, utilising the PRISM (Personal Reminder, Information, and Social Management) randomised field

trials, whereas Chen et al. (2024) conducted a prospective cohort study. A wide range of sample sizes was used: 99 participants in the study of Figueiredo *et al.*, (2020) was the lowest sample size and comparable to 100 participants (69 women and 31 men) in the study of Uchmanowicz *et al.*, (2020); 18,258 people with an average age range of 38 to 73 in the study of Chen *et al.*, (2024) was the largest; and 300 individuals ranging in age from 65 to 98 in the research of Czaja, Moxley and Rogers, (2021).

There were, however, some variations in the originality of the sample population. For example, Figueiredo *et al.* (2020) examined a population in Belgium with a mean age below 60, Uchmanowicz *et al.* (2020) investigated a population in Poland with an average age of 70, Chen *et al.* (2024) explored a population from the UK Biobank, and Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers (2021) researched a population in the US. Figueiredo et al. (2020), Uchmanowicz et al. (2020), and Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers (2021) used sociodemographic and clinical questionnaires to collect data. Symptoms of anxiety, male gender, age less than 60 (middle to older age), a lower academic level, a lower monthly household income, recurrent hospital admissions, and comorbidities like CVD were included in the socioeconomic questionnaire.

Clinical questionnaires used in the study by Figueiredo *et al.* (2020) considered LVEF, past hospitalisation, comorbidities such as atrial fibrillation, persistent kidney disease, type 2 diabetes, and elevated blood pressure, as well as NYHA functional classes I to IV. However, similar questions were also asked in the study by Uchmanowicz *et al.* (2020), with a few variations, including basic demographic information (gender, age, education, place of residence, occupation, and relationship status) and medical information (such as length of disease, prior cardioversions, hospital stays, indicators of AF, and complications). On the other hand, Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers (2021) conducted the PRISM randomised field trials. Chen *et al.* (2024) *gathered data from participants in visits 0 (2006–2010) and 1 (2012–2013) in the UK Biobank, with a mean interval between visits 0 and 1 of almost 4.2 years.*

All four research studies used completely different instruments to collect data, but they all used the same depression scale. Some scales were used to measure the data, such as the Hospital Anxiety Depression Scale (HADS), which was common in both studies

(Figueiredo *et al.*, 2020; Uchmanowicz *et al.*, 2020), the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) for depressive symptoms, and the Tilburg Frailty Indicator (TFI), one of the conventional tools used to measure vulnerability by Uchmanowicz *et al.* (2020). Figueiredo *et al.* (2020) used the Minnesota Living with Heart Failure questionnaire (MLwHF), which included questions about an individual's overall, emotional, and physical health, as well as ventricular function, measured by the NYHA (New York Heart Association) functional class I to IV. The parametric beta regression model and the nonparametric regression analysis were two multivariate models used to determine statistical and clinical significance (Figueiredo *et al.*, 2020). Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers, (2021) measured depressive symptoms using the Centre for Epidemiological Depression Scale (CESD), social isolation using the Friendship Scale, loneliness using the UCLA Loneliness Scale, social support using the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL), and social network size using the Lubben Social Network Index. Chen *et al.* (2024) used the Depression scale, a social isolation index score ranging from 0 to 3, and cardiovascular magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to evaluate cardiac activity. Furthermore, Chen *et al.* (2024) divided social isolation and loneliness into four categories: never, transient, incidental, and chronic. Their results also differed from those of Figueiredo *et al.* (2020), who showed a connection between Heart Failure and a lower ejection fraction and worse MLwHF. Anxiety and depression symptoms were found to negatively impact heart failure patients' quality of life, as indicated by beta regression. The negative impact of New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional classes III and IV on MLwHF was further supported by the regression tree. On the other hand, Uchmanowicz *et al.* (2020) found that 38 per cent of the 100 AF patients had mild FS and 29 per cent had significant FS. GDS scores showed that 51% of the patient samples had depressive symptoms, whereas HADS ratings showed that 28% of the patient samples had depression symptoms. Regression analysis showed that the GDS score of patients with AF was a reliable predictor of frailty syndrome in this clinical group, and 20% of participants reported feeling anxious. The distribution of participants across social exclusion categories was reported in the study by Chen *et al.* (2024). Those who experienced temporary social isolation made up 81.1%, incidental social isolation made up 5.8%,

chronic social isolation made up 6.7%, and those who experienced no social isolation made up 6.4%. Over an average follow-up period of 8.3 years, which included 3707 incident CVD events and 856 deaths (310 deaths due to CVD), ongoing social exclusion and chronic solitude were linked to a higher risk of occurrence of CVD, overall, and fatal CVD events compared to never experiencing social isolation. Similar conclusions were drawn from a study conducted by Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers (2021), which found a substantial correlation between depression and self-evaluation of well-being and loneliness.

Conversely, increased social isolation and decreased social support were associated with greater feelings of loneliness (Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers, 2021; Chen *et al.*, 2024). Loneliness acted as a mediating factor in the relationship between social isolation and health. Among older cohorts (those over 80), higher levels of social isolation were linked to smaller community networks, greater functional restrictions, and difficulties participating in significant hobbies. Seniors with functional limitations and who participated in less fulfilling activities were more likely to experience social isolation and loneliness (Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers, 2021). It was most likely the case that logistical obstacles to participation stemmed from functional constraints. Due to changes in living circumstances, people in the older age cohorts, especially older women, were more likely to live alone and had fewer resources available for assistance (Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers, 2021).

Theme 3: Older cardiac patients seeking health-related information online for self-care and the impacts of self-care and social support to improve cardiac health among them:

Only two studies (Zhu *et al.*, 2023; Jo, Ji Seo and Son, 2020) were found that conducted analyses to improve self-care behaviours among cardiac patients. While Jo, Ji Seo, and Son (2020) gathered data from South Korea, Zhu *et al.* (2023) conducted research in China. Both investigations were carried out in Asia, but in distinct countries. The study by Zhu *et al.* (2023) employed a population size of 451 old Chinese individuals with coronary artery disease from July to November 2021; however, the

study by Jo, Ji Seo, and Son (2020) contained almost half of the count with LVEF above 50%, and 87.3% (220) were NYHA class I–II, consisting of 252 elderly patients and this indicated that sample sizes varied widely. The age distribution of the participants was 60–92 years, with a mean age of 69.88 ± 6.43 in the sample population of Zhu *et al.* (2023), and the average age was 73 years in the study of Jo, Ji Seo, and Son (2020). The ways the data were gathered also varied: Jo, Ji Seo, and Son (2020) utilised medical records and structured questionnaires, whereas Zhu *et al.* (2023) employed a self-reported questionnaire. Data evaluation techniques also differed; for example, Zhu *et al.* (2023) measured the input of patients, used the Scale for Social Support Ranking, the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES), the Digital Healthcare Information Searching Scale, and the Scale for Self-Efficacy to measure self-efficacy, while Jo, Ji Seo, and Son (2020) used a hierarchical regression approach.

The results of both studies differed, despite their shared goal of improving self-care habits. Zhu *et al.*'s (2023) study, which used a structural equation modelling approach, indicated that patient engagement had both direct and indirect effects on online health data searching through self-efficacy. Social encouragement increased people's motivation to look up medical facts online through self-efficacy, and these results provided a theoretical foundation for developing and evaluating interventions to enhance older adults' capacity to access online medical information and improve self-care habits. Study results from Jo, Ji Seo and Son (2020) Concluded that the average follow-up duration after HF diagnosis was 8 years. Self-care habits were impacted by clinical and sociodemographic factors such as ageing, living with family, and stroke as a comorbidity. People aged 81 and older showed significantly higher levels of self-care than those aged 80 and younger, and people living with family demonstrated higher levels of self-care than those living alone. When concomitant heart failure and stroke were compared in older adults, the former group had higher levels of self-care than the latter (Jo, Ji Seo and Son, 2020).

4. Discussion:

4.1 Interpretation of findings and comparisons within wider literature:

The goal of this systematic review was to determine the impacts of social isolation and loneliness on the incidence of cardiovascular diseases among older adults aged 65 years and above. Additionally, online health information-seeking behaviours and sources among the elderly, and the impact of social support on reducing CVD incidents and improving health outcomes, were also explored. When carrying out research, three themes were identified, including theme one as the relationship between CVD incidence, social isolation and loneliness prevalence, the second theme was about the poor quality of life and mortality caused by CVD incidents and social isolation, and the third theme was about social support reflecting improvements in health outcomes among the elderly. Findings from seven studies demonstrated that cardiovascular health deterioration and heart failure incidences were quite common among older adults due to less social support, social isolation and loneliness, and two studies reported their urge to seek health information online, about two studies reported the ways to overcome these incidences and how social support improves overall health outcomes. Additionally, two studies reported that the quality of life of the elderly was worsened because of social isolation, loneliness and ageing.

For cardiovascular disorders (CVDs), such as cerebrovascular accidents, heart attacks, and coronary artery disease (CAD), age is a significant non-modifiable contributor to risk. (Fadah, Hechanova and Mukherjee, 2022). In the US, CVD continues to be the most prevalent cause of death, as in 2016, the expected number of deaths worldwide attributed to CVD was close to 17.6 million. (Fadah, Hechanova and Mukherjee, 2022). According to a systematic review and meta-analysis by Valtorta *et al.* (2016), a 29% rise in the incidence of cardiac event risk and an additional 32 per cent rise in stroke risk were linked to insufficient social interactions. However, this systematic review had limitations because the inclusion criteria did not specify an age limit.

The studies included in this systematic review were from a wide range of countries; however, specific focus was on developed countries like US, UK and China, because cardiovascular diseases among elderly, mainly due to social isolation, are not limited to any specific region but in developed countries the reasons are hectic lifestyles of the family members, loss of a partner, hearing loss, chronic illnesses and disabilities, retirement, generalized frailty that prevents them from going out regularly, necessitating assistance with mobility but not receiving it. As in research by de Koning *et al.* (2021) Both loneliness and social exclusion were associated with active engagement and sedentary behaviour among older adults (mean age, 73 years).

The results of this systematic review were thoroughly examined, taking into consideration the numerous factors that contributed to social isolation and loneliness, cardiovascular diseases in the elderly population, the role that social support played in lowering the prevalence of these conditions, the increased frequency with which older adults search medical knowledge via the internet and the consequences of this behavior, as well as some research gaps and critical analysis.

4.2 The prevalence of loneliness and social isolation in older adults:

The population of elderly individuals is growing at a faster pace compared to previous decades, as according to estimates from the Census and Statistics Department, (2017), the percentage of people 65 and older would climb from 17% in the year 2016 to well above 31% in the year 2036 and then to 37% by the year 2066. In a qualitative study by Park *et al.* (2019), 25 Asian migrants in New Zealand, including older adults speaking Chinese and Korean, aged between 76 and 84 years, were analysed using a thematic analysis approach. The results depicted that loneliness and social exclusion constituted serious, even catastrophic, obstacles for these elderly individuals, which was mainly because of language obstacles, accommodation, regularity, availability, and the cost of recreational and social events, and similar significant problems they encountered, and their social connectivity was least impacted by their tenure of residence in New Zealand. Moreover, these findings were consistent with one of the

studies in theme 1 of this systematic review, Czaja, Moxley, and Rogers (2021), which had a larger sample of 300 participants from the USA.

Similar to the findings of Czaja, Moxley and Rogers (2021), another study by Gerst-Emerson and Jayawardhana (2015) Examined panel information from the Health and Retirement Study (2008 and 2012) to ascertain how well loneliness contributed to increased medical services consumption among older adults in the US aged 60. The findings from applying adverse binomial regression models indicated that hospital admissions were not substantially associated with loneliness, but chronic loneliness was significantly associated with multiple physician visits. A systematic review of qualitative studies by Akhter-Khan *et al.* (2024) Investigated loneliness prevalence in underdeveloped and developing countries with several political, socioeconomic, societal, and financial variables, with participants of young and middle ages, irrespective of gender, from East, North and West African countries, South, Southeast and west asian countries. According to the findings of qualitative investigations by Akhter-Khan *et al.* (2024), refusals, desperation, a lack of employment opportunities, impoverished circumstances, and unfulfilled expectations among young adults and adolescents were among the primary characteristics of loneliness. However, these findings differed from older adults' loneliness features, as older adults have different desires in old age that are more closely linked to social support than to employment or relationship refusals.

Consistent with the findings of Golaszewski *et al.* (2022), Cené *et al.* (2012), Coyte *et al.* (2022), and Guo *et al.* (2023) from this systematic review, the incidence of social isolation and loneliness was also explored by O'Sullivan *et al.* (2021), but it was from the COVID-19 pandemic era. It was concluded that social exclusion was more prevalent during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially among older people, due to quarantine restrictions, the financial crisis, and ageing. In a randomised controlled study conducted by Williams-Farrelly *et al.* (2024) during the COVID-19 pandemic in the USA, 603 primary care recipients aged 65 and older were enrolled, and the study aimed to determine the association between isolation and both mental and physical quality of life. The Spearman correlation analysis showed that feeling isolated was not significantly associated with physical quality of life. However, it was moderately associated with

mental quality of life, anxiety disorder severity, and depressive symptom severity after correction for sociodemographic characteristics (Williams-Farrelly *et al.*, 2024). Although it was the opposite of this systematic review's findings, which were adhering to social isolation that was more likely linked to physical health, especially cardiovascular health, by Chen *et al.* (2024), but this was similar to the previously mentioned study of O'Sullivan *et al.* (2021) about covid pandemic effects.

In line with the conclusions of Yarish *et al.* (2024), which looked into social isolation and loneliness status among veteran U.S. women, another cross-sectional study by Straus *et al.* (2022) included 4069 older US military veteran participants utilising data from the National Health and Resilience in Veterans Study (2019-2020). The study's analysis concluded that 56.9% of military personnel reported feeling alone occasionally (37.2%) or frequently (19.7%), and that the degree of isolation was associated with a range of problems in psychological, physiological, and behavioural wellness. Compared to seldom experiencing loneliness, experiencing loneliness frequently or occasionally was linked to a three times higher chance of having suicidal thoughts. It was different from the findings of Yarish *et al.* (2024), which concluded that veteran women experienced more loneliness than non-veteran women. It was about women, whereas the Straus *et al.* (2022) study analysis had no gender specifications.

4.3 Effects of loneliness and social isolation on general quality of life and heart function:

As Figueiredo *et al.* (2020) explored the impacts of AF (atrial fibrillation) on the prevalence of depressive symptoms. People need social assistance to overcome social exclusion, the examination of narrative themes by Freak-Poli *et al.* (2022) Considered the relationship among social wellness (less social separation, greater social interaction, and less loneliness) and post-CVD physical wellness among Australian and New Zealander residents, and the results concluded that improved mental wellness results (few symptoms of depression, feelings of anxiety, and emotional discomfort) had been systematically linked to better social health, and this was due to social interactions. Among people with cardiovascular disease, improved social well-being was associated with better psychological outcomes and met patients' needs.

However, Freak-Poli *et al.*, (2022) concluded a very contrary fact in comparison with the findings of Czaja, Moxley and Rogers, (2021) Who found that a broad social network was linked to reduced loneliness, and that higher levels of loneliness were associated with worse self-ratings of health? While, Freak-Poli *et al.* (2022) Assessed that housing circumstances and relationship status were inconsistent with social assistance and isolation, and also examined that unsatisfied patient demands were linked to isolation from society, a decline in social interactions, and a shift in connections to an informal caregiver role; however, higher adherence to medications was linked to marriage or cohabitation.

Similarly, interesting study findings by Newman-Norlund *et al.* (2022) This study analysed 62 healthy individuals aged 60-80 years who had been living in social isolation for only 1 month. The study found that during the period of social isolation, the quality of life of older individuals declined dramatically, with the most significant drops. Individuals who engaged in greater levels of exercise and had improved mental and physical wellness before isolation tended to experience more progressive declines in their quality of life within 1 month of isolation. Additionally, Kuiper *et al.* (2015) Concluded in their systematic review that social isolation was strongly associated with the incidence of dementia, reducing the quality of life among older adults.

As women are emotionally more fragile due to multiple physical causes and hormonal imbalance challenges compared to men, Golaszewski *et al.* (2022) Investigated postmenopausal women for the prevalence of social isolation, loneliness and CVD incidence, and results demonstrated coherent findings of postmenopausal women having a high prevalence of these disorders; however, a systematic review analysis by Bedaso *et al.* (2021) Research on pregnant women revealed that there were strong correlations between less social support and the likelihood of anxiety, depressive symptoms, and self-harming incidents during pregnancy.

(Albasheer *et al.*, 2024) performed a meta-analysis, comparable to the study analysis of Hu *et al.* (2021) and Christiansen *et al.* (2021), to ascertain the connection between loneliness and social exclusion and the chances of middle-aged and older adults acquiring CVD. A total of 104,511 individuals from six studies were chosen. Between 4

and 13 years after, on average, 5073 cardiovascular incidents were observed; the frequency of social isolation ranged from 2% to 56.5%, and that of loneliness from 5% to 65.3%. Inappropriate connections to society were linked to a 16% higher incidence of CVD.

4.4 Interventions to overcome social isolation/loneliness and to improve quality of life:

According to the findings of Figueiredo *et al.* (2020), which explored variables that worsen QoL, older people's involvement in volunteer endeavours may benefit their personal wellbeing, help build financial assets, and enhance their integration into the community. (Gil-Lacruz, Saz-Gil and Gil-Lacruz, 2019) Conducted a global analysis involving 1699 people, with a mean age of 61 to 80 years, including 476 people from Spain, 901 people from Mexico, and 798 people from Chile. Self-reported personal fulfilment, contentment, and overall wellness were measured on a scale of 1 (excellent) to 5 (extremely poor) for data management. The results demonstrated that, although working for religious or social activities proved advantageous for both genders' levels of contentment, it was not as suitable for men's levels of life satisfaction in terms of social awareness, as evidenced by their self-reported data when measured on a satisfaction scale. (Gil-Lacruz, Saz-Gil and Gil-Lacruz, 2019). However, volunteering frequently had a greater effect on men's well-being than on women's. Similar findings were examined in a prospective evaluation by Barron *et al.* (2009) One hundred seventy-four elderly volunteers participating in Experience Corps Baltimore were the participants. Fair, good, and poor states of health were used to stratify outcomes, and the majority of participants reported higher levels of stamina and strength at the time of volunteering. Individuals who were in fair health were substantially more inclined compared to those in good health to show an enhanced pace of climbing stairs and medically significant improvements in speed of walking.

However, Jo, Ji Seo and Son (2020) investigated greater personal care habits among 81 years above elderly cardiac patients living with their families, similarly Pobrotyn *et al.* (2021) also inquired the decrease of multiple hospital admissions and unexpected medical appointments by proactively involving individuals in the personal care

procedures with 403 CHF (chronic heart failure) patients being admitted to the hospitals. Their findings revealed important contrary information that male gender was an adverse predictor of self-care because men were more inclined compared to women to be financially secure, employed for a longer duration, and thus devote less spare time to medical education and self-care behaviours.

More interesting findings on managing social isolation by Shorey and Chan (2021) in a systematic review of studies from Asia, North America, and New Zealand, showing that elderly individuals experienced psychological challenges and insufficient interpersonal support from close family members. Hence Shorey and Chan, (2021) concluded that elderly migrants resorted to volunteered social interactions, adopted going on walks with local people to establish their own cultural groups, to become close to one another via socially significant activities, to work toward the creation of more cohesive societies and participated in religious activities for spiritual satisfaction as coping mechanisms just like Jo, Ji Seo and Son, (2020) who concluded about self care behaviours to reduce social isolation.

To document evidence on the consequences of technological strategies to reduce social detachment and loneliness among older people across contexts outside medical centres, Welch et al. (2023) conducted an evidence and gap map analysis. According to the analysis, most of the measures that improved the quality of life and reduced feelings of isolation and depressive symptoms involved electronic measures that improved communication with relatives, close friends, and community members through phone calls and video conferences, and especially with professional robotic assistants and simulated animal companions which were utilized as alternatives to the human companions to reduce subjective lonely feelings.

However, like Welch *et al.* (2023), Fogelson, Rutledge, and Zimbardo (2022) investigated how automated animals could improve the quality of life for senior citizens during the COVID-19 pandemic, and the study found improvements in loneliness and despair. Additionally, individuals were actively involved in their partner animals, who offered fulfilling leisure and satisfying memories.

4.5 Policy implementations to reduce social isolation/loneliness:

As few studies in this systematic review were from the UK, therefore in the UK, there were Government strategies in place to help loneliness during and after covid, not apparent in any other countries and a specific strategy in which Gov UK (2018) launched the first National Loneliness Agenda and appointed the first Minister for Loneliness in history during Covid-19 Pandemic to tackle the loneliness prevalence. Three set goals included finding out consequences, causative factors, and strategies for addressing loneliness, to include the idea of isolation in all aspects of governmental policy, acknowledging the myriad of variables mitigating feelings of loneliness and promoting social wellness and perseverance among people, and the third goal was to start a public dialogue on loneliness and increase understanding of its detrimental impacts. It was also mandated that NHS England and the Department of Health and Social Care would continue to be dedicated to enhancing and growing the social prescribing programs that link individuals to local organisations in managing loneliness, and leading cross-government efforts to combat loneliness would continue to be the responsibility of the Minister for Sport and Civil Service (Gov UK, 2018). The UK government provided grants of £2.6 million to support upgrades to communal areas, enabling individuals to interact and work together to overcome loneliness (Loneliness Annual Report, 2020). Progress of the strategy showed that according to statistics from the Community Life Survey (2023), the percentage of mature adults in England who experienced ongoing loneliness remained unchanged at 6% for the last five years from 2018 to 2023; Yet, since 2018, a better knowledge of the categories that were more vulnerable to persistent loneliness had been gained and improved strategic plans were to be implements consequently (Gov UK, 2023).

Another action plan was put up by the World Health Organisation (WHO) in 2020, which encompassed the period from 2021–2030 and was designed to tackle factors lowering quality of life amongst older people as well as promote healthy ageing, and the Global Strategy and Action Plan on Ageing and Health (2016–2030) served as its foundation. Its goals included no starvation, no impoverishment, optimal physical and

mental wellness for all senior citizens, and gender equality. Two initiatives, specifically for the elderly, addressed the issue of preventing financial distress by outlining the need for benefits such as social security, adaptable retirement strategies, tax-funded basic pensions, and access to future health and medical care (UN Decade of Healthy Ageing: Action Plan, 2020). Lifelong development is essential for healthy ageing, allowing elders to engage in activities they enjoy, maintain their decision-making skills, and maintain their freedom, objectives, and dignity, thereby preventing feelings of loneliness. For that purpose, WHO (2020) proposed that skill development and free-of-obstacles engagement regarding digital skills were prerequisites.

(Progress report on the United Nations Decade of Healthy Ageing 2021-2023, 2023) documented outcomes of the healthy ageing action plan, in which following four metrics showed over 20% rises in execution within 2020 and 2022: bringing laws prohibiting bias due to growing older, supporting older adults's utilization of assistive technology through law, putting a national program for elderly-friendly communities and towns, and bringing a national policy on thorough evaluations of social and medical desires.

This systematic review has partially answered the research question as most of the findings from the included studies concluded more about social isolation and loneliness causing more physical impairments, including cardiac diseases among elderly; however, wider literature comparison revealed that it was the mental health which was significantly impacted due to loneliness and social isolation among elderly and physical health including CVD incidences were coming after. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic exaggerated social isolation and loneliness among the elderly, leading to a significant spike in mental illnesses; however, study findings from this systematic review did not find enough data about the impacts of COVID-19 on social isolation and loneliness, as this pandemic was a sudden and significantly impactful cause with a long-lasting tail of disorders.

4.6 Strengths and Limitations:

The strengths of this systematic review are given as follows:

The systematic review approach has been used because it is a structured methodology for representing, extracting, and interpreting findings from primary studies. The findings of this study are helpful for public health policy makers to reduce social isolation and consequently the incidence of CVD among the elderly and reduce healthcare costs to cure heart disease and other mental health issues caused by loneliness and social isolation. A wider range of participants was selected, which helped them obtain more reliable study results. However, the target population was a specific older age group, and participants from developed countries were included, so the findings cannot be generalised globally because underdeveloped countries were not included. The impacts of other comorbidities like diabetes, vascular illnesses and other disabilities on the development of social isolation and loneliness and then consequently the incidence of CVD, have not been discussed in detail.

One of the most significant limitations is that only CVD incidences were kept under consideration because of social isolation and loneliness; however, more exhaustive literature research has demonstrated that mental health was more affected, in addition to anxiety and depression, due to a lack of social assistance. Secondly, the COVID-19 pandemic and the impact of quarantine restrictions on social isolation and loneliness have not been adequately explored. This domain should have been discussed to yield more valuable study outcomes, as one of the most significant spikes in social isolation and loneliness occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic was an abrupt, significant factor that had an ongoing impact on several medical conditions. More research from low-income countries should have been included to make a valuable comparison of incident CVD and the prevalence of social isolation/loneliness among elderly individuals in both low- and high-income countries, which could help medical service providers formulate policies accordingly. Another limitation was that only a few studies included middle-aged participants, despite their intriguing and pertinent results, thereby skewing the study's overall conclusions.

6. Conclusion:

Ageing is a non-modifiable risk factor for the development of cardiovascular diseases. However, social isolation and loneliness also play a significant role in the prevalence of heart disease among the elderly. 13 articles were included in this systematic review, using PICO, PRISMA guidelines, and a PRISMA flow diagram to screen and finalise the included studies. The available data concerning older adults who were socially isolated and lonely, the emergence of cardiovascular disease in them, CVD-related mortality and the role that technological innovation and social assistance play in overcoming these variables were compiled in this systematic review. Incidents of CVD among the elderly were found to be influenced by social isolation and loneliness, particularly among veterans when they were compared with non-veterans. Older adults in developed countries like the United States, the United Kingdom, China, Denmark, and Brazil are often associated with social isolation and loneliness. To deal with these concerns, a variety of coping strategies, such as volunteering, engaging in religious activities, video calls with friends and family, owning robotic pets, and engaging with professional simulated assistants, were found to be effective.

Additional analysis of the literature research indicated that social isolation in older people was creating anxiety and depressive symptoms, which meant that mental health was somehow targeted equally or more than physical illnesses, including CVD. Furthermore, it was discovered that the poor quality of life experienced by elderly individuals who suffer from loneliness was a result of their social isolation, heart failure, atrial fibrillation, atherosclerotic disorders, and they marked their health ratings as low quality. On the other hand, social support and self-care behaviours were linked to better health outcomes, increased energy and stamina among older adults, and online health information-seeking behaviours helped people improve their perceptions and quality of life. Elderly people with CVD who lived with their life partners exhibited higher medication adherence behaviours that improved health outcomes, as did older adults, especially those 80 years of age and older, who lived with relatives and showed better self-care habits.

Elderly Asian migrants in New Zealand experienced catastrophic health outcomes due to social isolation and lonely feelings, which were mainly caused by communication barriers, accommodations, frequency, accessibility, and the expense of recreational and social endeavours. In contrast to older individuals, middle-aged and younger people were found to be lonely due to rejection, hopelessness, a lack of career opportunities, and substandard living circumstances in developing and underdeveloped nations. Moreover, it was discovered that more medical expenditure was going to the treatment of social isolation and loneliness, as long-term loneliness in the elderly was linked to an increase in doctor's visits. Older adults had to endure living in social isolation during the COVID-19 pandemic due to quarantine regulations, financial hardships, and ageing.

The UK government's proactive action plan, which included a substantial budget of 2.6 million pounds, brought a ray of hope for older adults grappling with social isolation (Loneliness Annual Report, 2020). This plan aimed to identify and support specific groups enduring persistent loneliness, even though the overall number of social isolation victims remained unchanged. The World Health Organisation (WHO) also stepped in with an action plan on healthy ageing, targeting the identification and resolution of social isolation, housing conditions, financial instability, and other barriers to healthy ageing, in collaboration with relevant local government agencies. These initiatives provide a beacon of hope for the future of elderly care.

Few studies have been conducted on low- and middle-income countries, even though their citizens experience stress, loneliness, and depression until their old age due to factors such as financial instability, substandard housing, inadequate education, and limited career opportunities. Some of these studies have found excellent results regarding the incidence of cardiovascular disease (CVD), poor health outcomes, social isolation, and loneliness among developed countries with adequate healthcare facilities. To support older people who are socially isolated or lonely, this systematic review's findings can assist healthcare services and social programs in developing interventions that emphasise technology, active coping skills, and organised lay-led activities. The goal of this systematic review was to address a challenge that is becoming increasingly important due to its effects on the well-being of older individuals and on global medical

and social welfare infrastructures. Hence, by recognising the kinds of treatments that minimise or avoid social exclusion or depression and the circumstances under which they work best, this analysis will facilitate policymakers with a better understanding of how to cope with these issues.

7. Future recommendations:

- The findings of this systematic review highlight the crucial role of social support from family, friends, and community in reducing hazards that may impact senior citizens' cardiovascular health and overall quality of life. This emphasis on the power of community can make the audience, including legislators and medical professionals, feel the importance of their roles in informing the public about this issue.
- More research should be done about the prevalence of social isolation during the COVID-19 pandemic, as it impacted everyone globally, and quarantine restrictions added a layer on top.
- More studies to explore the impacts of loneliness on the development of mental disorders are needed.
- The role of less social assistance in carrying out daily life activities leading to the development of loneliness should be discussed in future, as there are no nursing homes in underdeveloped countries that can help the elderly in routine life activities.
- The middle-aged population is the most stressed age group in developing and underdeveloped countries, as they have a load of responsibilities, and they should be the target population for future research in terms of the development of CVD and social isolation.
- Pregnant and postmenopausal women should be included in further studies regarding the development of social isolation and loneliness
- Mechanisms of the development of social isolation should be taken into consideration.

- More studies in the future should focus on the development of sources of health information available to the elderly. This is a crucial area that requires attention, as not all older adults have access to the internet, smartphones, or laptops at all times. By addressing this issue, we can potentially improve the health and well-being of a significant portion of the elderly population.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation Full Form / Description

AF	Atrial Fibrillation
ARIC	Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities
ASCVDRS	Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease Risk Scale
ASPREE	ASPirin in Reducing Events in the Elderly
BHF	British Heart Foundation
CASP	Critical Appraisal Skills Programme
CAD	Coronary Artery Disease
CESD	Centre for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale
CHF	Chronic Heart Failure
CINAHL	Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature
CI	Confidence Interval
CVD	Cardiovascular Disease
FRS	Framingham Risk Score
FS	Frailty Syndrome
GDS	Geriatric Depression Scale
GP	General Practitioner
HADS	Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale

Abbreviation Full Form / Description

HF	Heart Failure
HR	Hazard Ratio
IQR	Interquartile Range
ISEL	Interpersonal Support Evaluation List
JBI	Joanna Briggs Institute
LVEF	Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction
MLwHF	Minnesota Living with Heart Failure Questionnaire
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
NYHA	New York Heart Association
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (if mentioned in later policy context)
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PRISM	Personal Reminder, Information, and Social Management
QoL	Quality of Life
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
SD	Standard Deviation
SI	Social Isolation
TFI	Tilburg Frailty Indicator
UK	United Kingdom
UK Biobank	Large-scale biomedical database and research resource (UK)
UN	United Nations
WHO	World Health Organisation

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8. Appendix:

1. CASP checklist for appraisal of cohort studies:

1. Did the study address a clearly focused issue?
2. Was the cohort recruited acceptably?
3. Was the exposure accurately measured to minimise bias?
4. Was the outcome accurately measured to minimise bias?
- 5 (a) Have the authors identified all the important confounding factors?

(b) Have they taken account of the confounding factors in the design and/or analysis?

- 6 (a) Was the follow-up of subjects completing enough?
(b) Was the follow-up of subjects long enough?
- 7 What are the results of this study?
- 8 How precise are the results?
- 9 Do you believe the results?
- 10 Can the results be applied to the local population?
- 11 Do the results of this study fit with other available evidence?
- 12 What are the implications of this study for practice?

2. JBI CHECKLIST:

1. Were the criteria for inclusion in the sample clearly defined?
2. Were the study subjects and the setting described in detail?
3. Was the exposure measured validly and reliably?
4. Were objective and standard criteria used for measurement of the condition?
5. Were confounding factors identified?
6. Were strategies to deal with confounding factors stated?
7. Were the outcomes measured validly and reliably?
8. Was an appropriate statistical analysis used?

